

GREEN PEAS - USEFUL CROP

D. Ochilboyev, TDAU branch of Samarkand, student

Z. Bobokulov, Samarkand branch of TDAU,

associate professor, PhD

Abstract: Compared to cereal crops, legumes are rich in protein, essential amino acids, and vitamins and contain up to 20–40% protein. Among the legumes, green peas are important. Green peas are the most widely grown leguminous crops for food and fodder purposes. The seeds of blue peas ripen well and are digested quickly. Green peas are considered the main source of protein in fodder production, one nutritional unit of which is 120–180 grams of digestible protein. The stem contains 6–4% protein. Also, nodule bacteria live in a symbiotic state on blue pea roots and accumulate 80–120 kg of nitrogen per hectare during the growing season, increasing soil fertility.

Key words: legumes, lentils, food, food unit, protein, immunity, budding bacteria, feed unit.

Today, along with the market economy, the demand for agricultural products is also increasing. Providing the population with quality nutrients is one of the main goals of the agriculture sector. Cotton, wheat, soybeans, and many other types of crops are currently the most cultivated crops in agriculture. We can include green peas among these crops. Green peas are among the leguminous crops grown as the main and secondary crops, and today we can find them on the tables of residents of many developed countries. Green peas are a valuable food product rich in protein.

Looking back at the history of the green pea, green peas were one of the first legumes cultivated for human consumption. It is known from the literature that

greenpeas were cultivated 5000 years ago. This tasty and nutritious product contains many vitamins and antioxidants, which is why green peas are loved all over the world. Green peas are also a source of protein. It breaks down well in the body and replaces protein obtained from animals. Green peas perform the following functions in the human body: one of the first legumes cultivated for human consumption. It is known from the literature that greenpeas were cultivated 5000 years ago. This tasty and nutritious product contains many vitamins and antioxidants, which is why greenpeas are loved all over the world. Greenpeas are also a source of protein. It breaks down well in the body and replaces protein obtained from animals. Green peas perform the following functions in the humgreen peas metabolism and blood circulation; strengthening muscles and bones. From the literature, it appears that green peas were cultivated 5000 years ago. This tasty and nutritioGreen peasct contains many vitamins and antioxidants, which is why greenpeas are loved all over the world. Greenpeas are also a source of protein. It breaks down well in the body and replaces protein obtained from animals. Green peas perform the following functions in the human body: metabolism and blood circulation; strengthening muscles and bones; fighting against diseases and fatigue; and strengthening the cardiovascular system. At the same time, green peas are also considered a dietary product that helps with weight loss.

Since green peas are digested faster than beans, mung beans, and other legumes, it is recommended to give them to children as one of the first legume products. If 8- to 9-year-old children are given a delicious puree of green peas, they will eat it with love. At this age, the child's body requires the protein and other substances contained in green peas, so the child's body produces the necessary enzymes that help digest such foods. Nowadays, we can also see clotted green peas on the market stalls.

It should be noted that green peas retain their vitamins even when canned. At the same time, green peas have been used in medicine for many years. Regular consumption of canned green peas is rich in antioxidants that eliminate toxins and allergens and can cleanse the human body down to the cellular level.

It is of great importance to prevent skin, hair, and nail problems for people who eat green peas. At the same time, green peas also have medicinal properties, and we can cite the following as an example: If you drink 200 grams of blue pea tincture once in the morning, your voice will become clearer, your color will improve, and if you gargle with a toothache, the toothache will remain. At the same time, green pea flour is useful for malignant tumors and cancer, diarrhea, and cough.

In summary, the protein content of the blue pea grain, which is one of the legume crops, includes lysine, methionine, tryptophan, threonine, valine, phenylalanine, leucine, isoleucine, and histidine for animals and birds, among the essential amino acids for humans. It is more important than other crops due to the abundance of arginine compared to other crops.

References

1. Tukhtamishova, J., & Bobokulov, Z. (2022). Peas-Protein Source. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE*, 1(6), 62-63.
2. Page, D., & Duc, G. (1999). Peas, a promising source of protein. *Oleagineux Corps Gras Lipides (France)*.